

A Tool for Risk Evaluation of Autonomous Vehicle Integration in Traffic Environments

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Abstract—The integration of AVs into existing transportation systems presents significant challenges, including safety, infrastructure adaptation, and public acceptance. To address these issues, a structured risk assessment framework is essential for guiding decision-making processes. This paper studies the application of the AHP as a decision-support tool for evaluating the risk associated with AV integration. Focusing on three critical risk categories - hazard, vulnerability, and exposure - this study uses AHP to assess and prioritize risks. A case study based on the IN2CCAM European project is presented to evaluate the potential impact of AVs in both urban and extra-urban traffic environments. KPIs are identified, and the relative weights of various risk factors are determined. The results indicate that the hazard category has the greatest impact on the integration of AVs, with the probability of accidents being the most critical factor. However, social acceptance, production costs and charging infrastructure limitations also play an important role in determining the feasibility of AV adoption.

Index Terms—Autonomous Vehicles, AHP, KPI, GTI

I. INTRODUCTION

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), developed by Thomas L. Saaty in 1980 [1], is a widely recognized decision-support method that simplifies complex decision-making scenarios, particularly in the context of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs). As research and development of AVs continues to evolve, their integration into transportation system presents critical challenges, including safety, infrastructure adaptation, and public acceptance. Addressing these challenges requires robust decision-making frameworks capable of handling multiple risk factors simultaneously. In this context, it is crucial to adopt structured methods such as AHP to assess risk factors. AHP facilitates this by decomposing complex problems into a hierarchy of simpler criteria, helping decision-makers manage uncertainty and conflicting factors effectively.

Research supported by the IN2CCAM project (EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme Grant Agreement No. 101076791). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

This approach combines subjective assessments and mathematical analysis to derive priorities and support informed decisions. Unlike other decision-support methods, AHP is particularly advantageous for AVs as it allows for a systematic evaluation of both qualitative and quantitative factors, ensuring a comprehensive risk assessment.

AHP method stands out for its flexibility, ease of use, and ability to integrate multiple criteria. It has been adopted in areas such as risk management, strategic planning, and the evaluation of technological alternatives.

One of the key aspects of this research is the use of AHP to compare standard vehicles and AVs. By establishing a structured evaluation framework, this method enables a systematic comparison of risk factors, helping to identify the critical differences between these two transportation paradigms.

In particular, this study applies AHP within the European IN2CCAM project, which focuses on the full integration of Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) services into transport systems. A key element is the use of this method to determine the relative weights of different Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), ensuring a uniform and comparable impact assessment across different Living Labs (LLs). These KPIs contribute to the evaluation of the Global Traffic Indicator (GTI), a comprehensive metric used to assess the overall impact of AVs deployment on urban traffic. By incorporating AHP into the IN2CCAM methodology, a structured prioritization of risks and performance measures can be achieved, facilitating better decision-making for AVs integration.

This paper aims to explore the application of AHP focusing on three critical risks factors: hazard, vulnerability, and exposure. Understanding these factors is essential to assess the risks associated with the integration of AVs into existing transportation systems. The objective is to establish a priority scale for these risks, ultimately aiding in decision-making regarding AV deployment. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II provides a review of related

work on risk assessment and decision-support methods for AVs, Section III presents the case study focusing on the European IN2CCAM project, Section IV presents the results, Section V makes a comparison between standard vehicles and AVs, and Section VI discusses key findings and future research directions.

II. RISK ASSESSMENT AND DECISION-SUPPORT METHODS FOR AVS

To integrate AVs into today's transportation systems, several challenges need to be addressed. Safety concerns, infrastructure adaptation, and public acceptance require a structured approach to assess multiple factors simultaneously. Several methods, such as fuzzy logic ([2] and [3]) and Parsimonious AHP [4] have been explored for the assessment of risk of AVs. In this context, the AHP stands out as a decision support tool that allows for a structured multi-criteria assessment, making it suitable for risk analysis in the context of AVs.

AHP is a multi-criteria decision-making framework that allows for systematic evaluation of alternatives based on multiple criteria. The method involves several key steps [5].

The first step of the AHP is Problem Decomposition, which involves breaking down the main problem into smaller, structured sub-problems. This hierarchy consists of five fundamental levels: the general objective, sub-goals, criteria (in this study, the KPIs of the European project), sub-criteria, and the stakeholders involved [6]. This structured approach ensures a clear and systematic evaluation.

Once the hierarchical structure has been defined, each criterion and sub-criterion must be evaluated to determine its relative importance in AVs risk assessment. This phase involves pairwise comparisons, where each element is compared against another to assess its priority.

The comparisons are expressed using the Saaty 1-9 numerical scale [7], to determine the relative weight of each factor. The resulting comparison matrix forms the basis for calculating the weights of the elements in the analysis.

The final step of AHP involves the synthesis of priorities. Once the pairwise comparison matrices have been constructed, the decision-maker derives the local weights of the factors at each hierarchical level and aggregates them to obtain global priorities.

The AHP method also allows testing the coherence of the judgments provided. The results are considered coherent if all the relationships between the criteria are correctly respected.

The strength of AHP lies in its ability to incorporate both qualitative and quantitative aspects [8] into the decision-making process, which makes it particularly suitable for evaluating AVs where various criteria are involved.

As pointed out by Bakioglu and Atahan [9], prioritizing risks associated with AVs requires a method that can address complex multi-criteria decision-making problems involving both tangible and intangible criteria.

The study carried out by Raj et al. [10] explores the challenges of AVs adoption, using the Grey-DEMATEL method to

analyze the interrelations between public acceptance, infrastructure, and regulatory barriers, complementing multi-criteria decision-making approaches. The study highlights that the AVs adoption involves addressing these interconnected challenges, which is crucial for effective risk assessment and prioritization in the integration of AVs.

The study conducted by Zhang and Tak [11] explores a variant of the AHP method, providing a different perspective on improving the reliability of risk evaluations in AV-related scenarios by optimizing the correlation between performance metrics and the risk of the test scenarios.

A case study applied to a European project will be presented, illustrating how these tools are used in practice to prioritize risks in the development and integration of AVs.

III. CASE STUDY

The IN2CCAM European project (full title: *Enhancing Integration and Interoperability of CCAM eco-system*) is an Innovation Action funded under the Horizon Europe program. The project aims to integrate CCAM services into fleet and traffic management systems as part of the CCAM Partnership, with the goal of accelerating the deployment of automated, cooperative, and connected mobility technologies and systems [12]. The consortium's objective is to design and implement innovative solutions for connected and automated vehicles, infrastructure, and users, catering to both passenger and freight transport needs.

The IN2CCAM project is structured through six LLs that will implement the full integration of CCAM services into transport systems.

The aim of the project is to achieve full integration of CCAM services and to develop innovative proposals to accelerate the adoption of these technologies. A specific methodology has been developed to assess the impact of the proposed solutions. This assessment includes a series of key steps and the identification of KPIs grouped according to the impact areas.

The adoption of the AHP method to determine the relative weights of the different KPIs ensures a uniform and comparable assessment of impacts in different LLs. This approach also includes stakeholder consultation for each LL and the conduct of specific surveys.

Within the IN2CCAM project, it was considered essential to have a methodology and a reference framework to evaluate the impact implied by the integration of AVs fleets in city traffic. The criteria taken into account are the KPIs. These indices contribute to the evaluation of the GTI.

IV. APPLICATION AND RESULTS

This section presents the application of the AHP method to the case study and its analysis results. The main objective is to evaluate the risks associated with AV integration in urban and extra-urban traffic.

Based on the analysis, three main categories of risks have been identified: hazard, vulnerability and exposure. Each category has been further broken down into sub-criteria linked to the project's KPIs:

- Accident rate: percentage of accidents involving AVs, normalized directly.
- Accident severity: the percentage of accidents resulting in injuries or fatalities.
- Traffic queue length: assessed between 0 meters (no queue) and 50 meters (equivalent to 10 vehicles).
- Waiting time at traffic lights: range from 0 minutes (no waiting) to 20 minutes.
- Sudden decelerations: percentage of decelerations in relation to kilometers traveled.
- Technical failures: failure rates in sensors, mechanical systems and software.
- Environmental factors: presence or absence of adverse weather conditions.
- Production, charging and parking costs: normalized according to defined ranges.
- Social acceptance: percentage of negative responses in questionnaires.
- Pollutant production: comparative values of CO₂ and NO_x emissions between scenarios.

Hazard has been evaluated through accident rates, traffic efficiency indicators (as queue lengths, signal wait times), decelerations, and potential failures in mechanical, electronic, and software components. Tools like SUMO simulations and Python algorithms have been used to assess these risks.

The vulnerability risk focuses on adverse environmental factors such as weather conditions affecting AV sensors, and Internet connection disruptions, both of which are critical for real-time decision-making and safe operations.

Finally, exposure risk addressed economic (production, charging, and parking costs), environmental (pollutants generated during charging), and social acceptance factors. User surveys highlighted key preferences and concerns, revealing that cost, safety, accessibility, and efficiency are pivotal for acceptance, particularly among diverse demographics such as commuters, individuals with disabilities, and high-income travelers.

In the evaluation process, surveys have been conducted with experts in the transportation sector, using the Saaty scale (1-9) [13] to compare criteria and sub-criteria. The data has been organized into comparison matrices and relative weights have been derived.

After defining the 16 sub-criteria for comparison, corresponding to the 16 KPIs considered in the evaluation of the GTI, comparison matrices have been developed to collect decision-maker's assessments. Specifically, two types of pairwise comparison analyses have been conducted following two distinct hierarchies.

In the first hierarchy, all 16 comparison criteria have been assessed at the same level, resulting in a 16x16 evaluation matrix. Relative weights have been assigned based on subjective judgments, occasionally supplemented by findings from previous analyses addressing similar issues. For each pair of criteria, a question has been formulated as follows: "*For the evaluation of the GTI, how much more important is criterion A compared to criterion B?*". Verbal assessments (e.g., equally

important, more important, less important, etc.) have been translated into numerical values. The evaluation scale ranged from 1 to 4.

Table I shows the weight evaluation by comparing all the criteria with one another.

In the second hierarchy, three separate matrices have been constructed to evaluate the sub-criteria associated with three primary categories: hazard, vulnerability, and exposure. This resulted in three comparison matrices of dimensions 8x8, 2x2, and 6x6, respectively. The number of pairwise comparison has been significantly lower than in the first analysis. The numerical assignment procedure for each comparison followed the same methodology as in the first hierarchy, using the same evaluation scale.

Starting from the complete matrices, the overall weight of each KPI in contributing to the GTI has been calculated. In particular, the priority synthesis phase has been performed using a Python library to simplify and lighten the strictly algebraic component of matrix calculation. The chosen library has been *pyDecision* [14], which includes the resolution of many of the most widely used MCDA methods in the literature.

Each of these three criteria has been assigned the same weight in the GTI evaluation. Therefore, to calculate the weight of each sub-criterion for the GTI, it has been necessary to divide each result obtained from the algorithm by three.

Below are two graphs (Figure 1 and Figure 2) that make the results obtained clear and explicit, highlighting the importance of each criterion and the differences in the two types of analyses conducted.

In detail, as can be seen in Figure 1, the risk criteria that have been found to be most critical are decelerations, sensor and electronic failures and software failures.

The criterion related to the social acceptance of AVs has been also found to be of primary importance. This aspect has also been strongly underlined by previous studies in which it was assessed that the lack of acceptance by consumers is among the main obstacles to the adoption of AVs.

In the second type of analysis conducted, as shown in Figure 2, the criteria that are most important are those related to the risk of vulnerability of the AVs: environmental factors, in detail adverse climatic factors, and the possibility of internet interruption.

In particular, we highlight the evident usefulness, ease of use, clarity of the results and the relative interpretation that the application of the AHP method allows for the study and evaluation of various aspects concerning the problem of the integration of AVs. The results obtained offer a clear and universally understandable hierarchy of risks priorities, so that in research, development and production frontiers it will be possible to place particular emphasis on these priority risk factors.

The results have shown that the hazard criterion has obtained the highest weight (0.45), followed by vulnerability (0.35) and exposure (0.20). Among the sub-criteria, the probability of accidents has been the most relevant, indicating the need to focus efforts on detection and response technologies.

TABLE I
WEIGHT EVALUATION BY COMPARING ALL CRITERIA WITH EACH OTHER

GTI		Hazard										Vulnerability			Exposure						
		Acc. rate		Acc. severity		Traffic		Dec.		Sensors Electronics		Failures		Env. Factors	Internet dis.	Cost		S. Acc.		Pollutant Prod.	
		Queue	T. lights	Queue	T. lights	Sensors Electronics	Mechanical	Software	Env. Factors	Internet dis.	Prod.	Ch.	Park.	Prod.	Co ₂	No _H					
H	Acc. rate	1	3	2	1/4	1/3	1/3	1/2	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/3	1/3	1/3	
	Acc. severity	1/3	1	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/4	1/4	
	Traffic	2	4	1	1/3	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/3	2	4	1/3	3	3	
	T. lights	1/2	3	1/3	1/2	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/3	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/3	2	1/2	1/2	1/3	1	1	
	Decelerations	4	4	3	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	4	4	2	4	4	2	4	4	
	Sensors	3	4	2	1/2	1	2	3	4	4	4	3	2	2	2	4	4	2	3	3	
	Elec.	3	4	2	1/2	1/3	1	2	3	3	3	1	1/2	2	3	3	3	1	2	2	
	Mech.	3	4	2	1/2	1/2	2	4	4	4	4	2	1	4	4	3	4	2	3	3	
	Soft.	3	4	2	1/2	1/2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	4	4	3	4	2	3	3	
	Env. Factors	2	3	2	1/2	1/3	1/2	1	1	1	1	1/2	1/4	2	2	1/2	4	1/3	2	2	
	Internet disruptions	3	4	3	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/2	1/2	1	1	1/3	1/4	1	1	1/4	1/2	1/3	1/2	1/2	
	Prod.	2	3	1/2	1/2	1/4	1/3	1/2	1/2	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/4	4	1	1/2	3	2	4	4	
Ch.	2	3	1/2	1/4	1/3	1/3	2	2	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	2	2	1	2	1/3	3	3		
Park.	2	4	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/3	1/4	1	1/3	1/2	1	1/4	1/2	1/4		
S. Acc.	2	3	3	1/2	1/2	1	1	3	1/2	1/2	1	1/2	3	1/2	3	4	1	3	3		
Co ₂	3	4	1/3	1/4	1/3	1/2	1/2	2	1/3	1/3	1/2	1/3	2	1/4	1/3	4	1/3	1	2		
No _H	3	4	1/3	1/4	1/3	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/3	1/3	1/2	1/3	2	1/4	1/3	4	1/3	1/2	1		

Fig. 1. Weights obtained from first hierarchy

Fig. 2. Weights obtained from second hierarchy

V. AHP FOR COMPARISON STANDARD VEHICLE VS. AUTONOMOUS VEHICLE

The last phase of this research consists in the representation of a hypothetical (but realistic) scenario, where GTI values have been calculated using the weights previously obtained for a scenario with AVs integrated into traffic and another scenario with only traditional vehicles. The main objective is to determine in which of the two scenarios the GTI has a lower value, since a lower GTI reflects a lower negative impact on traffic conditions and management.

For the analysis, the KPI values obtained from simulations or usage statistics have been normalized to a range of 0 to 1, according to the characteristics of the scenario evaluated.

The GTI is defined as the weighted sum of all considered KPIs. Each normalized KPI is multiplied by its previously determined weight, with the results derived from the initial AHP application. These evaluations, detailed in Table I, provide a

TABLE II
EXCLUSIVE USE OF TRADITIONAL VEHICLES KPIS

KPI	Weight	KPI Value	Normalized Value	Contrib. to GTI
Accident rate	0.020	22%	0.22	0.00484
Accident severity	0.010	5%	0.05	0.00055
Traffic queue length	0.030	20 m	0.40	0.013733
Waiting time at traffic lights	0.020	6 min	0.30	0.0052
Decelerations	0.080	7%	0.07	0.005507
Technical failures	0.070	1%	0.01	0.000348
Mechanical failures	0.040	5%	0.05	0.002233
Software failures	0.060	no	0	0
Environmental factors	0.22	0	0	0
Internet disruptions	0.11	no	0	0
Production costs	0.090	€ 35000	0.03	0.002618
Charging costs	0.070	€ 1.80	0.20	0.014133
Parking costs	0.02	€ 0.50	0.25	0.004333
Social acceptance	0.090	20%	0.20	0.018200
CO ₂	0.040	100%	1.00	0.036333
NO _x	0.030	100%	1.00	0.029000

TABLE III
INTEGRATION OF AVs KPIS

KPI	Weight	KPI Value	Normalized Value	Contrib. to GTI
Accident rate	0.028	17%	0.17	0.00476
Accident severity	0.017	2.80%	0.03	0.000476
Traffic queue length	0.058	25 m	0.50	0.029
Waiting time at traffic lights	0.028	6 min	0.30	0.0084
Decelerations	0.143	5%	0.05	0.00715
Technical failures	0.139	3%	0.03	0.00417
Mechanical failures	0.093	1.60%	0.02	0.001488
Software failures	0.126	0.90%	0.01	0.001134
Environmental factors	0.061	0	0.00	0
Internet disruptions	0.04	1.20%	0.01	0.000480
Production costs	0.059	€ 95000	0.38	0.022559
Charging costs	0.050	€ 0.50	0.61	0.030263
Parking costs	0.03	€ 0.50	0.25	0.007500
Social acceptance	0.088	55%	0.60	0.0528
CO ₂	0.020	70% less	0.20	0.004
NO _x	0.019	75% less	0.15	0.00285

structured approach to assessing each KPIS actual contribution to the GTI.

In the worst-case scenario, the GTI reaches a maximum value of 1, indicating that all risk factors correspond to the most critical possible conditions.

The first scenario considers the exclusive use of traditional vehicles. In this case, some KPIS had to be excluded since no data could be obtained on them and therefore they did not represent a source of risk for a traditional vehicle. In fact, software failures and internet interruptions were assigned a value of 0.

The evaluated KPIS are shown in Table II.

The second scenario examines the integration of AVs, incorporating specific KPIS related to AVs, as shown in Table III.

The results obtained highlight a key insight: the scenario

without AV integration yields the lowest GTI and therefore, under current conditions, no AV integration represents the most favourable option. This conclusion underlines the challenges associated with AV integration, particularly in economic and social terms.

In the scenario with full AV integration, the key factors influencing the results are social acceptance, production costs, charging costs and queue length. It should be noted that the criteria identified as most critical in the AHP assessment do not always emerge as the most influential in a real-world scenario. For example, even though the KPI related to decelerations receives the highest weight, its actual impact on GTI remains relatively minor. This discrepancy is justified by the high level of reliability that AV integration entails, which reduces the frequency of severe decelerations caused by software or sensor failures. Consequently, the perceived risk of such events remains low under normal operating conditions.

A particularly striking result is the significant role of social acceptance in determining the viability of AV integration. Despite not being the highest priority KPI initially, public perception and trust in AVs are decisive factors, suggesting that technological advancement alone is insufficient: broader social acceptance is crucial for widespread adoption. Similarly, cost factors pose substantial barriers to integration. From the results it can be deduced that AV adoption will only become viable when production and operation costs decline at a steady pace (e.g. by 15-20% annually), making AVs a competitive alternative to traditional vehicles. Furthermore, the long-term viability of AV technologies extends beyond private self-driving cars, encompassing shared mobility solutions such as autonomous shuttles and buses [15], which could improve accessibility and efficiency in urban transport.

For the first scenario, with the lowest GTI, pollution-related KPIS had the greatest influence, which was predictable. However, this comparison is inherently limited by the inability to account for certain risk factors unique to human-driven vehicles. In this study, an idealized scenario has been taken as a reference, where human drivers maintain maximum attention and expertise, which does not fully reflect real-world driving conditions.

Finally, trust in AVs (and consequently their social acceptance) can be significantly improved through continued research and development. Projects such as IN2CCAM contribute to optimizing the integration of AVs by addressing critical barriers and refining methodologies to assess their impact.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the implementation of a multi-criteria approach for the analysis of risks related to the use of AVs. The three risk factors of hazard, vulnerability and exposure and the related sub-criteria are considered. Through the use of the AHP, it was in fact possible to provide a clear and traceable framework for the assessment of the importance of the various criteria involved and, consequently, for the evaluation of the respective priorities for the decision maker.

The results of the comparison between the exclusive use of traditional vehicles and the full integration of AVs highlight the effectiveness of AHP as a decision-support tool for managing the complexities of AV integration in urban and extra-urban mobility systems. In particular, the analysis highlighted the importance of considering some criteria, such as decelerations, sensor and electronic failures, social acceptance, as priorities compared to others.

Finally, this research contributes to optimizing AV integration strategies by identifying key risk factors and their relative importance. Projects as IN2CCAM and other similar initiatives can leverage these insights to improve policy recommendations, infrastructure planning, and public engagement strategies, ensuring a balanced and well-informed approach to the adoption of autonomous mobility.

Regarding future developments, it would be interesting to expand the study by including new risk factors and increase the opinion of additional experts in the field. Furthermore, the integration of other decision support methodologies could further enrich the analysis and provide even more detailed and useful results for decision makers.

The proposed approach is confirmed to offer a solid basis for future research and practical applications, contributing to the improvement of urban mobility systems and the diffusion of innovative technologies in the field of transport.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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